

Research Article

Impact of the National Health Insurance Authority-Health Maintenance Organisation Authorisation code system on the knowledge, attitude, and practice related to hypertension among National Health Insurance Authority-enrolled outpatients in a tertiary hospital, Federal Capital Territory

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Summary

Background: Hypertension is a globally significant health burden, with a prevalence rate of nearly 49%. However, the clinical and economic burden is high and continues to increase. The NHIA, in partnership with HMOs in a bid to mitigate the financial burden on Nigerians, has in some way been beneficial. The delivery of universal health coverage through this integration involves a chain of processes, including acquiring a Pharmacy Authorization Code to obtain medications to improve the quality of life. However, with the implementation of a monthly authorization code process, the impact on the KAP of hypertensive outpatients (towards hypertension management) enrolled in the insurance scheme is limited. This study assessed the impact of the NHIA-HMO pharmacy authorization code (PAC) system on the KAP of hypertension in NHIA-enrolled outpatients within UATH. It also seeks to identify potential barriers within the coding system.

Method: A cross-sectional study using a mixed-method approach was conducted with 345 hypertensive patients aged 18 years and above at UATH, Gwagwalada. A random sampling technique was used for the quantitative study, and data was collected through a validated, semi-structured questionnaire covering socio-demographics, KAP levels, and perceptions of the impact of the code system. The qualitative component utilized a pre-tested interview guide administered to purposively selected participants. Quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS (v27.02), while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis with visualization using ATLAS.TI (v25) and MS EXCEL (2019).

Result: Correlation and regression analyses showed that the NHIA-HMO Code significantly influenced attitude and practice ($r = 0.227, p < 0.001$; $r = 0.252, p < 0.001$) but had no impact on knowledge ($r = -0.023, p = 0.336$). The regression model indicated that the code system predicts changes in attitude and practice but explains only 8.3% and 11.7% of their variance, suggesting other influencing factors. Emerging qualitative themes such as "difficulty obtaining the code," "long waiting hours," and "lack of HMO

communication" highlight systemic challenges, whereas facilitators like "improved adherence, follow-up, and patient counseling" demonstrate its potential benefits.

Conclusion: The NHIA-HMO code system does not enhance knowledge about hypertension but significantly influences attitude and practice, encouraging medication adherence. However, bureaucratic delays hinder its effectiveness. Additionally, long-term NHIS enrollment or HMO selection does not necessarily translate to improved KAP.

Key words: Attitude, Authorisation Code, HMO, Hypertension, Knowledge, NHIA, Practice, Outpatients

Introduction

Background and significance

Hypertension is defined as having a systolic blood pressure (SBP) of ≥ 140 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of ≥ 90 mmHg, or taking medication for hypertension (WHO 2023a). Hypertension may be primary, which can develop due to various environmental or genetic causes, or secondary to renal, vascular, or endocrine disorders (Mackenzie et al. 2024). Modifiable risk factors include unhealthy diets (excessive salt consumption, a diet high in saturated fat and trans fats, and low intake of fruits and vegetables), physical inactivity, tobacco and alcohol consumption, and being overweight or obese. Additionally, environmental risk factors for hypertension and associated diseases exist, with air pollution being the most significant. Non-modifiable risk factors include a family history of hypertension, age over 65 years, and co-existing diseases such as diabetes or kidney disease (WHO 2024).

Mean blood pressure and the prevalence of raised blood pressure have declined substantially in high-income regions since at least the 1970s. By contrast, blood pressure has risen in East, South, and Southeast Asia, Oceania, and sub-Saharan Africa (Zhou et al. 2021).

Hypertension is a major contributor to cardiovascular disease, stroke, and kidney failure. According to the WHO (2023a, 2023b, 2023c), its prevalence has nearly doubled over the past three decades, affecting approximately 1.3 billion adults worldwide. Almost every 1 in 3 adults is hypertensive, with male prevalence slightly higher than females in the under-50-year age group. Beyond 50, the prevalence reaches nearly 49%, indicating that nearly every other individual is affected, with a prevalence that is almost equal among men and women. However, the clinical and economic burden of hypertension is high and continues to increase globally (Mancia et al. 2023).

To address such burdens, Universal Health Coverage (UHC) has been prioritised, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3.8), emphasising financial protection and access to quality care. The WHO (2023d) explains the concept of UHC as the stage when everyone should have access to quality health services without financial hardship. However, the world is off track to make significant progress towards universal health coverage (Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) target 3.8) by 2030.

A report by the European Commission (European Commission 2023) indicated that currently, at least half of the world's population does not have access to the health services they need, about 100 million people fall into extreme

poverty each year because of excessive health spending and over 800 million people spend at least 10% of their household income on healthcare.

In Nigeria, the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), which has recently been transformed into the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA 2024), partners with Health Maintenance Organisations (HMOs) to ensure equitable access. The NHIA-HMO partnership, which serves as a vital instrument in Nigeria's government efforts to achieve Universal Health Coverage, is an approach designed to ensure that healthcare is accessible to insured persons when needed without incurring Catastrophic Health Expenditure (CHE) (Sui et al. 2021). A core component of this system is the Pharmacy Authorisation Code (PAC), a monthly code required for accessing medications.

This study investigates the impact of the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA)-Health Maintenance Organization (HMO) authorisation code system on the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of hypertension among NHIS-enrolled outpatients in a tertiary hospital, as hypertension remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in Nigeria (Oguanobi 2021), thus making effective management essential. The NHIA-HMO authorisation code system, a crucial component of integrating HMOs with the National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA), plays a key role in ensuring access to healthcare services. However, despite its intentions, little is known about how this authorisation process affects patients' knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding hypertension management. Assessing its impact on KAP will help determine its effectiveness and inform policy decisions aimed at optimising hypertension care. Such an assessment will be achieved through the use of a mixed-methods analysis, which provides a comprehensive understanding by enabling analysis from rich data. Given that tertiary hospitals serve as critical healthcare providers, this study will offer valuable insights into the system's efficiency in these settings and its broader implications for healthcare accessibility and quality, with an additional aim of uncovering barriers and facilitators within the system.

Over the past two decades, the burden of hypertension in Nigeria has risen dramatically. According to Adeloye et al. (2021), the prevalence increased from 8.6% in 1995 to 32.5% in 2020, representing a significant rise from approximately 4.3 million to 27.5 million affected adults. Despite this alarming trend, awareness, treatment, and control remain poor, with only 29% of individuals aware of their condition, 12% receiving treatment, and just 2.8% achieving adequate blood pressure control.

This growing public health challenge underscores the need for more effective health system interventions, particularly through health insurance schemes. Evidence from across Nigeria, Ghana, and other low- and middle-income countries suggests that health insurance can have a positive influence on hypertension outcomes. Studies by Oseni et al. (2023) and Hendriks et al. (2016) found that insured patients were more likely to adhere to treatment and achieve better blood pressure control. Similarly, El-Sayed et al. (2015) showed that insurance helped reduce inequalities in access to care for non-communicable diseases, while Ogedegbe et al. (2018) demonstrated that integrating insurance with nurse-led care further improved hypertension management.

These findings suggest that while health insurance alone may not significantly improve knowledge and attitudes, it plays a crucial role in supporting treatment adherence and follow-up care, especially when combined with

quality service delivery and patient education. Strengthening the NHIA-HMO system in Nigeria could therefore be a key step toward addressing the rising burden of hypertension.

Objectives

- To assess the impact of the NHIA-HMO authorisation code system on hypertension KAP among NHIA-enrolled hypertensive outpatients.
- To explore the relationship between socio-demographic factors and hypertension KAP outcomes.
- To assess the relationship between the NHIA-HMO authorisation code system and KAP of hypertension among NHIA-enrolled outpatients.

Materials and methods

Study design and setting

A cross-sectional, mixed-method study was conducted between August 2024 and January 2025 at the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, a 550-bed tertiary institution in Nigeria.

Population and sampling

The study included NHIA-enrolled hypertensive outpatients aged 18 and above who had been enrolled in NHIA for at least one year. Cochran's formula: $n = (Z^2 \times p \times (1-p))/E^2$ was used to determine the sample size while considering variability in studies for a conservative estimation was used, with a confidence level of 95%, desired precision of 5%, and prevalence of 50%, the population size was 385. However, after mitigating for missing data, the adjusted sample size was 427. Thus, a total of 427 patients were selected via random sampling for the quantitative arm, while key stakeholders (healthcare workers, NHIA staff) and patients were selected purposively for interviews.

Instruments

Quantitative data were collected using a pretested, semi-structured 29-item questionnaire covering socio-demographics, KAP levels, and perceptions of the PAC system. The qualitative aspect employed a pre-tested interview guide.

Data collection and analysis

Quantitative data were collected by combining self-administration (using both online and paper-based methods) of quantitative instrument to patients and interviewer-administration of the qualitative data instrument to stakeholders and fewer patients; over 4 weeks. Interviews were conducted and recorded with patients and key stakeholders, and transcribed for qualitative analysis. Quantitative data were analysed using SPSS v27.02 with descriptive and inferential statistics (regression and correlation). Thematic analysis and visualisation of transcribed qualitative data were conducted using ATLAS.TI v 25 and MS Excel (2019).

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval with assigned number UATH/HREC/PR/2025/02/251 was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital (UATH), Gwagwalada, Abuja. Informed oral and written consent was secured from all participants, and confidentiality was strictly maintained.

Results

Demographics of respondents

A total of 345 participants completed the survey (81% response rate). The predominant age group of the respondents was 33–47 years (38.6%), and slightly more participants were female (51.9%) than male. Most were employed (72.5%), had tertiary education (47.0%), and were low- to middle-income earners (50.7%). Over half (52.5%) had been enrolled in an HMO for 11–20 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of Key Socio-Demographics.

Characteristic	Most Common Category	Percentage
Age	33–47 years	38.6%
Gender	Female	51.9%
Education	Tertiary	47.0%
Employment	Employed	72.5%
Income	₦50,000–100,000	50.7%
HMO Duration	11–20 years	52.5%

Knowledge of hypertension

Overall, respondents demonstrated good knowledge of hypertension. Most (90.4%) recognised normal blood pressure ranges, and 91.6% identified lack of exercise as a risk factor. However, fewer participants recognised symptoms like chest pain (46.4%) or complications like vision loss (52.8%).

Attitude toward hypertension management

Attitudes were generally positive. Approximately 78.3% of respondents expressed concern about their blood pressure, and 80.9% agreed that managing their condition was important. However, a significant number (64%) viewed medications alone as not very or not at all effective.

Practice of hypertension self-management

The study revealed that medication adherence was high, with 74.2% reporting consistent intake. Monthly monitoring was the most common practice (64.1%), and healthy diets and stress management were frequently employed. However, only 41.2% of respondents reported physical activity (Table 2).

Table 2. Summary of Self-Management Behaviors.

Behavior	Practicing Respondents
Consistent medication use	74.2%
Regular BP monitoring (monthly+)	92.8%
Healthy diet	96.2%
Stress management	82.6%
Exercise	41.2%

Impact of NHIA-HMO code system

Regression analysis revealed that the NHIA-HMO code system had a statistically significant impact on *attitude* ($r = 0.227, p < 0.001$) and *practice* ($r = 0.252, p < 0.001$) but not on *knowledge* ($r = -0.023, p = 0.336$). The system accounted for 8.3% of the variance in attitude and 11.7% of the variance in practice.

Qualitative insights

The thematic analysis yielded two broad categories:

- **Challenges:** The study highlighted some notable barriers, including difficulty obtaining codes, long waiting hours, and poor HMO communication, with difficulty obtaining codes being the most frequently occurring challenge (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Challenges frequency.

Figure 2. Facilitators frequency.

- Facilitators: Improved follow-up, counselling, and medication adherence, among other benefits, were identified as positive outcomes of the scheme, with the ability to access medications being the most highly perceived benefit (Fig. 2).

These findings underscore both the bureaucratic limitations and the potential of the system to support better hypertension control when implemented efficiently.

Discussion

Globally, health insurance systems in high-income countries, such as the USA, the UK, Canada, and European countries, generally improve healthcare access and patient outcomes. However, administrative challenges related to insurance processes, similar to the NHIA-HMO system, also exist. For instance, in the United States, the Medicaid and Medicare systems have authorisation processes that can delay care, similar to NHIA-HMO frustrations in Nigeria. However, health insurance has a positive influence on knowledge and self-management due to extensive patient education programs (Escarce et al. 2014), unlike the absence of such programs in Nigeria.

Across Africa, the impact of the NHIA on hypertension management varies. In Ghana, the scheme facilitates higher medication adherence due to fewer administrative barriers, although lifestyle changes remain limited (Oseni et al. 2023). Similarly, South Africa’s private insurance yields better hypertension KAP, while public sector patients like NHIA-HMO enrollees in Nigeria face delays, frustration, and inadequate patient education (Dennison et al. 2007).

Regional disparities in NHIA coverage across Nigeria offer essential context for interpreting the findings of this study. In the North East and North West, lower enrolment rates are primarily due to the limited presence of NHIA-ac-

credited facilities, which forces many patients to rely on out-of-pocket expenses. Similarly, in the South East and South West, NHIA coverage remains lower than in Abuja, with a greater dependence on private insurance or direct payments (Aregbeshola and Khan 2018). This study, conducted in a tertiary hospital in Abuja where NHIA infrastructure is comparatively stronger, still revealed that the NHIA-HMO authorisation code system had a weak or negative influence on patients' knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding hypertension management. The implication is that in regions with even less access to and support from NHIA, such challenges are likely to be magnified. If patients in Abuja face delays, poor communication, and inadequate support for self-management despite better NHIA coverage, then those in under-resourced areas may be even more disadvantaged in managing hypertension. These findings underscore the crucial need to enhance the NHIA system, not only by improving administrative efficiency but also by expanding accredited facilities and ensuring equitable access to patient-centred care across all regions of the country.

In conclusion, the NHIA-HMO code process does not improve knowledge about hypertension, despite improving attitudes; however, bureaucratic delays impact its effectiveness. However, one major benefit of the NHIA-HMO code process is its positive influence on most patients adhering to their medications, although it does not encourage comprehensive self-management. Lastly, long-term NHIA enrolment/HMO choice does not automatically lead to better KAP.

This study highlighted the similarities and differences in administrative challenges in the NHIA-HMO authorisation code system and patient outcomes, in comparison to other countries, thus enriching global discussions on the administrative and educational aspects of insurance-based care. It explored the impact of health insurance on hypertension management within the public health sector, highlighting the need for improved policies.

To this effect, the automation of approval codes is needed to reduce authorisation bottlenecks—automate approvals of code for routine care, as well as strengthening administrative efficiency by expanding accredited facilities, and ensuring equitable access to care across the country. There should be an open communication channel between HMOs and their clients to enhance communication and foster transparency. Structured patient education can be implemented through various learning tools and platforms by partnering with the relevant bodies. There is also a need to track patients' progress and adherence over time to boost confidence and improve compliance.

Furthermore, this study revealed that the challenges identified are not just peripheral but systemic and embedded, suggesting that even in a robust infrastructure, areas with weaker NHIA presence are likely to face even more severe challenges. Thus, there is a need not to reinvent the entire NHIA framework, but to adopt the aforementioned policies to effect targeted reforms. Also, although access to healthcare services is vital, it is insufficient without deliberate investment in patient empowerment.

Irrespective of these findings, the utilisation of correlational tests and the employment of a cross-sectional study pose a limitation to the study, as actual causal claims are not derived. The study lays the foundation for future longitudinal studies, which will evaluate the causal links between insurance coverage and the management of NCDs.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed oral and written consent was secured from all participants, and confidentiality was strictly maintained.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

AI tools were used in the language editing of the manuscript to improve its research tone. No AI-generated content was used for data analysis or interpretation.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: ZAG, MAN. Data curation: MAN. Formal analysis: MAN, IA, ZAG. Funding acquisition: JOA. Investigation: MAN. Methodology: MAN. Project administration: EHM, ZAG. Resources: MG. Software: MAN. Supervision: ZAG. Validation: IA. Writing – original draft: MAN. Writing – review and editing: ZAG, AMD.

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Data availability

The data underpinning the analysis reported in this paper are deposited at Data repository <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/5EQUFP>.

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